

EXTRAPOLATION CAPABILITIES OF DATA DRIVEN METHODS FOR COMBUSTION LES

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Abstract

We investigate a-priori the extrapolation capabilities two class of data driven methods - point and field regression models, for predicting sub grid scale flame surface density in LES of turbulent premixed combustion. While both approaches are actively studied, their relative performance across combustion LES relevant conditions remains insufficiently understood, especially beyond training distribution.

In this study, filtered DNS data are used to train multiple representative point and field regression data driven models. Their predictive performance beyond the training distribution is assessed in various combustion LES relevant conditions.

The findings indicate field regression architecture's robust extrapolation capability across scales and turbulent combustion conditions.

Introduction

Data driven methods are increasingly being investigated for combustion applications. In the context of combustion Large eddy simulation (LES), two main categories of machine learning methods are explored in literature: *Point regression methods* (PRM), which learn from point-to-point correlation with access only to local point data. *Field regression methods* (FRM) - which learns functions on 2D or 3D spatial fields, hence has information on distribution in the immediate region.

However, integration of FRM into CFD solvers is nontrivial [1] due to difficulties in intermediate steps such as interpolations, parallelization, wall regions treatment and uniform mesh requirement. Thus, it is essential to determine whether their increased complexity translates to better performance under combustion LES relevant conditions. Previous comparison studies have been limited to narrow range single parameter variation [2]. In this study we compare different classes of models in terms of their extrapolation ability across conditions such as mesh resolutions, equivalence ratios and Karlovitz number (Ka). While additional variations were explored, the results here discussed are limited to above mentioned conditions for brevity.

Methods

The objective of the data driven model is to learn filtered flame surface density ($\bar{\Sigma}$) as a function of the resolved progress variable gradient ($|\nabla\tilde{c}|$),

$$\bar{\Sigma} = f_{NN}(|\nabla \tilde{c}|) \quad (1)$$

where, f_{NN} is the data driven method employed, where, \tilde{c} is the progress variable calculated as $\tilde{c} = 1 - (Y_{H_2}/Y_{H_2,ub})$. The models are trained on two sets of premixed H₂ combustion DNS datasets, a slot burner [3] and freely propagating flame setups [4,5]. For training data, the DNS field is gaussian filtered and down sampled to a coarser mesh with a Down Sampling Factor (DSF = $\Delta_{LES}/\Delta_{DNS}$). Data processing techniques including normalization were employed, for FRMs additional preprocessing such as subdomain sampling and data augmentation were carried out. Five data driven methods were considered here, representing two class of data driven methods.

PRM: Standard artificial neural networks – Multi Layer Perceptron (MLP), Kolmogorov Arnold Networks and Random Forest Methods

FRM: an encoder - decoder CNN and Unet.

Results

Figure 1. a) Extrapolation performance of models trained with 4x mesh on coarser meshes. b) Truth vs prediction graph for ka1 and $Ka = 15 \cdot ka1$, the dashed line indicates maximum value seen during training with ka1 data.

Models were first evaluated across mesh resolutions. They were trained on the slot burner dataset with DSF of 4x (i.e., 4x coarser mesh than DNS). These models are then evaluated in increasingly coarser mesh. Figure 1a shows the normalized mean absolute error at different DSF meshes. All models show a similar trend with

increasing errors as mesh coarsens. But FRM methods have a significantly lower error than all the PRM models. All PRM models have very similar errors. The lowest error is observed with Unet, which can be attributed to its ability to learn multiscale structure.

Another set of models were trained with data from freely propagating H₂ flame from. Models were trained with low Karlovitz ($Ka = ka_1$) flame and their performance evaluated at higher $Ka = 15 \cdot ka_1$. Figure 2b shows performance of some of the models. Here a pattern was observed among PRM models. As the Karlovitz number increases the $\bar{\Sigma}$ increases. But PRM models fail for points with high $\bar{\Sigma}$ value. This threshold beyond which the prediction fails is similar across PRM and is approximately equal to maximum value the model sees during training. So, the PRM models fail when ($\bar{\Sigma} > \max(\bar{\Sigma}_{train})$). While no such threshold is seen with FRM models, indicating their robustness.

Figure 2. a) Integrated $\bar{\Sigma}$ flame surface density along axis; b) Relationship between model Input ($|\nabla \tilde{c}|$) vs output ($\bar{\Sigma}$); c) Truth vs prediction for RF and CNN

Further, extrapolation to different equivalence ratios (ϕ) was assessed with models trained on slot burner data at $\phi = 0.4$. At a higher $\phi = 0.7$, all models were able to extrapolate. But as equivalence ratio gets leaner, flame is more unstable due to thermodiffusive effects resulting in change of relationship between input and output quantity. This resulted in significant differences in the performances of PRMs at lower $\phi = 0.3$. Figure 2a shows underprediction of integrated $\bar{\Sigma}$ by all 3 PRM methods, while both FRM methods provide a good approximation. This performance difference is explained by truth vs prediction plot in Figure 2c. While CNN prediction shows good agreement, RF model shows underprediction. It is to be noted that the distribution by RF resembles the input - output distribution as in Figure 2b. This distribution is also seen across different PRM and FRM methods. This indicates that PRM methods merely reproduce the input - output distribution at different magnitude, rather than predicting the relationship between them. This indicates that they fail to extrapolate.

Conclusions and future work

The results reveal significant differences in extrapolation capability between the two classes of methods. FRMs demonstrated lower errors beyond training data, indicating their ability to learn multiscale structures across different combustion conditions. PRMs struggled to predict values higher than the training distribution. Similar relatively higher error predictions were observed across all PRM models. Since each of these PRM models differ significantly in architecture and yet they exhibit similar limitations. The results suggest that for combustion relevant LES conditions, local point wise information is insufficient to robust extrapolation. By incorporating 3D field information, FRMs were able to perform robustly across conditions tested here.

Future work will expand the range of conditions evaluated here and test these methods coupled with an LES solver to assess posterior performance.

Nomenclature

$\bar{\Sigma}$	Flame surface density
\tilde{c}	Resolved progress variable
Δ	Mesh spacing

Subscripts

<i>DNS</i>	DNS data variable
<i>NN</i>	Data driven method predicted quantity

Superscripts

*	Normalized
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